

DESTINATION MARKETING COMMUNICATION MODEL BASED ON TOURIST ATTRACTION AND HIERARCHY OF TOURIST NEEDS IN BOGOR REGENCY TOURISM VILLAGES

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Abstract

An interesting phenomenon after the pandemic in Indonesia is that many tourist villages are emerging. West Java has 469 tourist villages, 49 are in Bogor Regency. Tourist villages must build an attractive destination brand. They identify the Hierarchy of Tourist Needs for Visiting Tourist Villages and design a Tourism Marketing Communication Model to promote sustainable tourism villages. This research aims to create a Tourism Village Marketing Communication Model in Bogor Regency. Data collection methods include observation, in-depth interviews, and Focus Group Discussions. The results of research on the attractiveness of tourist villages found five unique elements for developing a destination brand: natural beauty (ecotourism) and agrotourism, tourism based on learning with nature (edutourism), arts and culture attractions and learning (cultural tourism), adventure in nature (adventure), and creative economy learning. The results of mapping the hierarchy of tourist needs that were fulfilled were only level 1, the satisfaction of the five senses enjoying the tourist village. Level 2 emotional touch in the form of joy and beautiful memories. Level 3 is interaction with residents and tourist village facilities. Level 4 in the form of satisfaction for tourists' self-development and level 5 of tourists' self-actualization has not been fully fulfilled.

Keywords: Tourist Attraction, Tourist Village, Destination Branding, Hierarchy of Needs, Marketing Communication.

INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 pandemic that occurred in various parts of the world, including Indonesia, has given rise to a new phenomenon, namely the increasing number of tourist villages emerging. BPS (Indonesia Central Bureau of Statistics) data shows that the distribution of the number of post-pandemic tourist villages in Indonesia over the last five years has continued to increase. At the end of 2019 when Covid-19 began, there were 135 tourist villages in Indonesia. In 2021 at the peak of the pandemic, it increased to 1,831 tourist villages, in 2022 when the pandemic subsided the number of tourist villages became 3,419, and in 2023 it will be 4,748 tourist villages. The Ministry of Tourism for more than a decade has carried out the "Wonderful Indonesia" tourism campaign at the global level to attract foreign tourists to visit various tourist destinations in Indonesia. However, as an agricultural country that has tens of thousands of villages, the campaign at the national or local level through "Pesona Indonesia" needs to be more focused by highlighting one of the important potentials to be developed, namely the management of tourist villages.

Village tourist destinations need to be developed into tourist destination brands by highlighting their uniqueness (including their unique characteristics or icons) and their special attractions (in terms of nature, culture, culinary, and others), various facilities are available, in addition to easy access to tourist village locations. Two things need to be done 1) identifying the hierarchy of needs of tourists (demand-side) who visit tourist villages. 2) Identifying and mapping the attractions of tourist villages (supply-side) that encourage tourists to visit. For this reason, a Tourism Village Marketing Communication Model is needed to promote tourism villages on an ongoing basis.

A tourist village is a rural area that has a special attraction for tourists through its natural potential, culture, and unique local activities (Ilianenko, 2005) (Widodo, B., Widyastuti, 2022). Bogor Regency has the most tourist villages, by 2023 it will have 41 tourist villages with three categories, namely pioneering, developing, and independent. Of the 41 tourist villages in Bogor Regency, six are the best tourist villages in Indonesia in 2023 (Diskominfo, 2023). The six villages studied, developed category, namely Batulayang, developing category, namely Pasir Eurih, Cilember, Tamansari, and Benteng.

The problem that occurs in tourist villages is the uneven distribution of the number of tourists to each tourist village. Apart from that, the potential attractiveness of tourist villages has not been identified and developed. The identification and mapping of the hierarchy of needs of tourists visiting tourist villages has not yet been carried out. No tourism village marketing communication model can be used as a reference for tourism promotion. The problem was discovered based on the results of initial observations of tourist villages. Tourist village managers have not yet identified the attractions and potential of tourist villages. We don't yet understand the segment of tourists who visit, especially the needs of tourists.

Tourist attraction is one of the determining factors in tourist visits which makes it a distinctive feature to visit (Salsabia Almas Andina, 2021). Carrying capacity in tourism includes unique attractions; accessibility; Facilities; and community involvement (T Titi Widaningsih., Mirza Ronda., Rahtika Diana., 2019) (Eka Gustiani Rokhayah, 2021). To attract tourists to visit tourist villages, developers must pay attention to several components which are the determining factors and supporting capacity for developing the attractiveness of tourist villages.

Tourist villages in Bogor Regency have a variety of diversity ranging from culture, creative economy, agrotourism, natural beauty, and the surrounding community environment. Each tourist village can highlight the advantages of this potential to make thematic tourist villages easy to recognize and remember for travelers. This potential diversity has not been managed and packaged well by tourism village managers, therefore there is still a lack of understanding, resources, and technology in identifying this potential. This hampered the development of tourist villages, making them a stopover place or just the name of a tourist village. This potential can be developed into a superior attraction in each tourist village so that tourists are interested in visiting. There are two interesting models to use when building a tourism destination brand. First, the three-dimensional model of Tourism Destination Branding (Tourist Destination Branding Model), is related to natural, cultural, and historical aspects as revealed by Iliachenko (Ilianenko, 2005). This model emphasizes the diversity of available tourist

destinations (supply side). From the tourist side, it is necessary to identify five hierarchies of tourist needs, namely: physiological needs, security needs, social needs, self-esteem needs, and self-actualization needs as the second model for analysis. The research objective is to identify the potential, carrying capacity, and attractiveness of the Bogor Regency tourist village. Mapping the hierarchy of tourist needs and developing a communication model for marketing tourism villages in Bogor Regency.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Based on the results of previous research, tourist motivation for visiting consists of: financial security (destination climate, transportation, amenities, institutions, tourist areas, natural and artificial), relaxation, escape, play, attraction, prestige and strengthening, leisure time, self-fulfillment, wish fulfillment, and social interaction (Euis Widiati, 2023). Factors that influence tourist visits are the attraction, amenities, accessibility, and ancillary (Regina Ceali Rengkung, Gene M.H Kapantow, 2024). Motivations that influence tourist visits include physical motivation where tourists want to refresh themselves or be free from routine activities. The cultural motivation of tourists is to want to know the tourist destination they are going to. Individual motivation, tourists want to visit family, and friends or look for new experiences. Motivation for status or prestige, tourists want to channel their hobbies, research, establish social relationships, and attend seminars or conferences (Serley Anggraeni Goutama, 2024).

Hierarchy of Tourist Needs in the Destination Brand Component consists of five levels of tourist needs, namely physiological needs, intangible needs, the need for relationships, self-development needs, and self-actualization needs (Balakrishnan, Melodina Stephens, Ramzi Nekhili, 2008) which were studied in this research can be seen in Figure 1

1. Physiological needs (Functional) in the form of real benefits, physical, biological, satisfaction, tangibles, relaxation, food, excitement, and stimulation.
2. Intangible Needs (Intangible): such as safety, security, comfort, access, service, and reducing anxiety.
3. Needs to Establish Relationships (Relationship Needs): interaction with travelers or other tourists, the management or atmosphere of the accommodation, and telling each other (getok-tular). Building the momentum of beautiful memories, having memorable experiences, reducing anxiety in interacting with other people, and affiliation with other parties. others, feelings of love, and other inner moods.
4. Need for Self-Development (Self-Esteem/Development Needs): namely the need for fame or popularity and destination reputation, gaining unique experiences, increasing status, increasing self-esteem, gaining recognition, personal achievement, fulfilling curiosity, expertise, and self-development.
5. Self-Actualization Needs (Fulfillment Needs): namely loyalty of tourists, various reasons for repeat visits, things that can strengthen self-expression, develop self-actualization, and share great experiences related to tourist destinations.

Figure 1: The Brand Component–Need Hierarchy Linkage

(Balakrishnan, Melodina Stephens, Ramzi Nekhili, 2008)

Another aspect studied in this research is the dimensions of tourist destination branding, namely (Figure 2): 1) dimensions of natural conditions: geographical location, climate or weather, landscape, etc.; 2) cultural dimensions: regional culture or local wisdom values (including culinary specialties), linguistic diversity, identity (ethnicity, ethnicity, general traditions and special traditions); and 3) historical dimension: regional history, history of destination development, and the influence of various parties in the region (Ilianchenko, 2005).

Figure 2: Three-Dimensional Model of Tourist Destination Brands (Ilianchenko, 2005)

There is a close relationship between the two models used in this research, namely the Three Dimensions of Destination Brands (supply side) and the Hierarchy of Tourist Needs in Destination Brand Components (demand side). This model was adopted by Balakrishnan, Nekhili, and Lewis (2008). This model will be used in the analysis of this research to map the hierarchy of tourist needs when visiting tourist villages in Bogor Regency. A destination brand or identity can form emotional attachments and fulfill tourists' needs. Important elements in brand asset management that are appropriate to the destination brand offering such as physical assets, images, and experiences play a role in attracting tourists by meeting their psychological and emotional needs.

The third concept used for analysis is the Marketing Communication Model which can be adopted for the Tourism sector as in Figure 3 from Chris Fill. According to Chris Fill, the important aspect of marketing communications is not only the message but also the brand and the media or techniques used. Messages must be consistent so that the public obtains information about the brand and processes the stimuli they receive, not only from advertising but from elements of the marketing communications mix, or even the brand itself (Fill Chris, 2009). The task of marketing communications is to present key messages as a stimulus to the target audience so that the audience remembers, repeats, and acts. These messages are not only through advertising but also through face-to-face activities in the field.

Figure 3: Marketing Communication Model (Fill Chris, 2009)

One-way or two-way stimuli will reflect a transactional or relational (collaborative) approach which determines the level of cognitive processing. The audience simply knowing (awareness), having a memorable experience (experience), involvement (involvement) or reaching the level of emotion or feeling, namely liking (likeability).

Build associations with the brand and memorable memories to form an attitude towards the brand or attitude towards the message. This has an impact on awareness and attitudes towards the brand as well as messages that influence purchase intentions. Brands and all marketing communication techniques in the form of a marketing communication mix such as advertising, sales promotions, personal interactions, events, and sponsorships, are needed to build or remind brand values and encourage action or behavior processes.

The attractiveness of each tourist village will be different, so it is necessary to identify this problem. Some things that are considered attractions in tourist villages include (1) easy accessibility, (2) tourism potential such as natural tourism, culture, art, legends, etc., (3) support from the surrounding community, (4) security, (5) accommodation, communication, and (6) climate (Dede Indra Permana, I Putu Gede, 2024). Another assumption states that factors in tourism development include (1) natural resources, (2) culture, (3) entrepreneurship, (4) finance, (5) labor, (6) competition, (7) society, (8) policy government in supporting tourism development (Fajar Rifai Putro Utomo, 2024).

What is considered the attractiveness of a tourist village is Uniqueness or Distinctiveness (Uniqueness), ease of access to transportation and online access (Accessibility), Facilities available (Facilities), Community Involvement (Community Involvement), Tourism Potential (Potential Tourism), Security, availability of lodging or Accommodation, various Communication programs carried out, conducive atmosphere or Climate, as well as Government Policy support, both from the central government and the government region/city. These ten components of tourist village attractiveness were studied in this research.

There is one component that influences tourists to visit, namely tourist motivation which is outlined in a hierarchy of needs including (1) physiological needs, (2) security needs, (3) social needs, (4) prestige needs, and (5) self-actualization needs (Hendra Syaiful, Agung Edy Wibowo, 2023). This component is interrelated between tourist attractions and needs when deciding to travel.

Tourist needs are internal factors that encourage tourists to travel to seek new experiences, to escape from routine. A destination's attractiveness is an external factor that attracts tourists to visit a destination through its natural beauty, cultural richness, tourist attractions, or recreational activities (Imam Ardiansyah, 2023).

METHODOLOGY

The focus of this research is to identify the carrying capacity of tourist destinations and tourist needs to be seen from tourist attractions and the hierarchy of needs of tourists visiting tourist villages in Bogor Regency. This research uses qualitative methods.

Data collection was carried out by observation, FGD, and interviews with the head of the Bogor Regency tourism office, tourism village managers, and practitioners in the tourism sector. The objects observed, identified, and mapped are tourism potentials that are unique or superior in building the attractiveness of tourist villages. The two models used in this research are the attractiveness of tourist villages and the Hierarchy of Tourist Needs in Bogor Regency Tourism Villages. Some of the challenges in tourist villages include infrastructure development that is not evenly distributed, inadequate access, tourist villages that are still difficult to reach, not yet optimal promotion, and not analyzing the potential advantages of these tourist villages (Pujiwiyanawa et al., 2018) (Hadi, 2022). In previous research, no one has identified the potential of attraction, and the hierarchy of tourist needs, especially in the tourist villages of Bogor Regency. This is a novelty in this research.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Attraction Mapping of Six Tourist Villages

The results of the research in the form of a profile and mapping of the attractions of six tourist villages in Bogor Regency found that the uniqueness or characteristics (in Table 1) that are attractive to tourist villages are five elements for developing a destination brand (destination branding) as one of ten types of tourist village attractions. namely:

1) Natural beauty (ecotourism) and agrotourism:

Ecotourism offers beautiful natural views, dense forests, and mountains. Bogor district agrotourism offers agricultural and plantation sectors where visitors can interact directly with agricultural and plantation activities. A combination of ecotourism and agrotourism, tourists can enjoy the beauty of nature while learning and participating in agricultural activities.

2) Tourism based on learning with nature (edutourism):

Bogor Regency offers Edutourism such as forest education programs, organic farming techniques, tea garden tours, learning to grow fruit, and so on. Edutourism offers an educational experience, providing insight into agriculture, nature conservation, and local culture. Edutourism teaches the importance of preserving nature while empowering local communities in the tourism sector.

3) Attractions and culture and art learning (cultural tourism, including cultural heritage):

The cultural tourism program offers cultural arts performances such as Angklung, Jaipong dance, and pencak silat. Making woven bamboo, traditional crafts, holding gamelan classes, learning traditional dance, and making batik with typical Sundanese patterns.

Making drinks such as wedang pala, wedang layang and traditional foods such as doclang, rengginang, getuk ubi. Various traditional rituals that tourists participate in to provide in-depth insight into the uniqueness of diverse local cultures.

4) Adventure in the wild (adventure):

Bogor district tourist villages offer various outdoor adventure activities including rafting, hiking, camping, flying fox, rock climbing, glamping, and outbound, challenging trekking. With beautiful views and a diversity of flora and fauna, adventure tourism in the Bogor district not only provides a fun, refreshing and adrenaline-pumping experience. Adventure tourism can increase awareness of the importance of preserving the environment.

5) Creative economy learning:

Organic agricultural products such as jam, fruit juice, and fresh vegetables are ready for consumption. Development of agrotourism and processed fruit products such as durian, rambutan, and other tropical fruits. Handicraft products such as woven bamboo, batik, and traditional musical instruments, such as typical Sundanese batik. Manufacture of functional products such as household furniture, wall hangings, footwear, shoes, slippers, and accessories. Making various traditional foods and drinks such as dodol, apem, wedang pala, soy milk, and other typical snacks which are attractively packaged and sold as souvenirs. Creative economy learning not only increases people's income but also adds useful learning experiences for tourists. The uniqueness or distinctiveness of each tourist village can be developed into a destination brand identity as shown in the following table.

Table 1: Characteristics of Uniqueness of Tourist Villages in Bogor Regency

No	Tourist Village	Tourist Attraction, Characteristic or Uniqueness
1.	Pasir Eurih	Creative and Cultural Tourism Village: Cultural arts performances, traditional food, Sibaginda Park, Jalatunda Well Site, Wedang Pala as a herbal drink, making shoes and slippers. Tour Packages: 3 packages of Mulih Ka Lembur, the Sawengi Ka Lembur.
2.	Tamansari	Ecotourism and Edu Agrotourism: Tea Garden, Kasmaran Studio: gamelan, Setu Tamansari, and Religious Complex: Temple, Vihara
3.	Batulayang	Ecotourism, Edutourism, Agrotourism, Adventure: Aesthetic Glamping, Exciting Outbound, Challenging Trekking, Twin Waterfalls, Natural Baths, Camping Ground, Tourist Lodge, ATV Offroad, Jungle Tracking, agrotourism package
4.	Cilember	Agrotourism, Creative Economy in the form of Cilember Waterfall, Pine Forest, Butterfly Park, Pencak Silat learning, Tracking, Kaulinan Lembur, Sawah Village, Kembang Kayu. Tour Packages: Wisawcil, Kembang Kayu and Live in
5.	Benteng	Edutourism, AgroTourism, River Tubing Fort, Catfish Biofloc, Soybean House, Ciwitan Batik, Hydroponics Village, Cassava Village, Suspension Bridge, Tofu Meatballs. Tour Packages: Pick crystal Guava, Ciwitan Batik "Lawon Geulis", creation of plastic packaging waste
6.	Cihideung Udik	Camping, cycling, trekking, training in making handicrafts or cooking traditional food

The results of identifying attractions in six tourist villages in Bogor Regency in terms of uniqueness, ease of accessibility, facilities, tourism potential, community support, security and health, accommodation, communication, natural conditions, and government policies can be seen in Figure 4

Figure 4: 10 Attractions of Six Tourist Villages in Bogor Regency

Another attraction is **accommodation** facilities in the form of the best cottages and villas in Batulayang, while homestays in the homes of residents of other tourist villages are standard, and culinary diversity is not yet prominent. There are various accommodation options to support a tourism experience that is close to nature and local culture. Simple accommodation to luxurious and comfortable villas. Accommodation in the Bogor tourist village offers a calm atmosphere and blends with the surrounding environment. Traditional homes are managed by residents. Villas and guest houses are suitable for families or groups. Resorts and accommodations that blend with nature, glamping equipped with mattresses, electricity, and private bathrooms. Bamboo lodges are for tourists who want to experience unique accommodation and unite with nature.

Figure 5: Example Of Tourist Village Accommodation In Bogor District

Access to tourist village locations in Bogor Regency varies depending on the geographical location of each village. Even though access to tourist locations is not too far from the center of Bogor city, not all the road infrastructure can be reached by large buses because the roads are small. Some areas still need infrastructure improvements for tourist comfort. Tourists can choose various types of transportation ranging from private vehicles, public transportation, and online transportation services.

Internet network access is not evenly distributed, depending on geographical location and the infrastructure available in tourist villages. Several tourist villages in areas that are more affordable than the city center have good internet access. Tourist villages in remote areas, hills or forests have limited network access. The availability of a good network will help optimize the tourist visiting experience.

Communication media are generally through online media and social media such as websites, Instagram, Facebook, TikTok, and YouTube. Tourism applications and platforms such as Google Maps are used to increase exposure. Traditional media such as brochures, pamphlets, and billboards are also used. Media has not been managed specifically and intensively with thematic content. Several face-to-face communication patterns are applied in several tourist villages. A good communication strategy also supports the creative economy and maintains tourism sustainability.

The tourism development potential for Batulayang is quite challenging because nowadays the unique Wedang Layang drink is available which is made from ginger, lemongrass, and orange. The types of tourism that are available and have the potential to be developed to be more attractive are Aesthetic Glamping, Exciting Outbound, Challenging Trekking, Twin Waterfalls, Natural Baths, Camping Grounds, Tourist Lodges, Offroad, Jungle Tracking, supported by the coolness and natural beauty of Batulayang. The development of tourist villages can take advantage of the attractiveness of forests, mountains, plantations, Sundanese culture, and the potential of the creative economy. By exploiting the existing potential, the Bogor tourist village can become an attractive and sustainable destination.

Figure 6: Examples Of Tourism Development Potential, Tourist Villages In Bogor District

Security and health care in several tourist destinations are good, such as in Batulayang which has a team of supervisors who are always on patrol to ensure the safety and comfort of visitors, there are health posts, well-maintained climbing routes, there are clear safety instructions, and health protocols are implemented. Some of the steps implemented in maintaining security and health care are the existence of village security posts, trained tourist guides, health centers, ambulance services, basic health facilities in accommodation, emergency communication facilities, and information and complaint posts. With these facilities and steps, the Bogor district tourist village can optimize tourist safety and health, create a safe tourist experience, and increase visitor confidence in returning. The Bogor district tourist village offers various facilities, including food stalls that serve regional specialties at affordable prices, and public toilet facilities at several points. Parking area for two-wheeled and four-wheeled vehicles. Accommodations, tourist information center, culinary center, souvenir shop, educational facilities, tracking route, photo spot, health facilities, gazebos, rest area, Wi-Fi and internet network facilities, traditional games arena and outbound facilities, educational facilities, worship area, board information, and road signs, campsites, tourist service centers. Adequate infrastructure can increase tourist satisfaction and encourage return visits. The community not only acts as a beneficiary but also as the main driver who supports the operations, promotion, and management of tourist villages (T Titi Widaningsih., Rahtika Diana., 2020). Several forms of community involvement and support in developing tourist villages in Bogor Regency.

- Open their houses as homestays so that tourists experience a unique and authentic experience.
- Sell local products, such as handicrafts, special foods, or agricultural products, in tourist villages.
- Become tour guides for tourists.
- Manage tourist destinations, such as cleaning the environment, maintaining security, and developing facilities.

Community involvement and support make tourist villages develop, creating economic and social benefits for the community. Strong community involvement can make tourist villages attractive, sustainable, and profitable destinations for all stakeholders.

Government support and policies of the Bogor district through the tourism and culture department include the Bogor regent declaring the Year of Tourist Visits with various activities such as cultural festivals, photo competitions, and special discounts for tourists; building a Tourism Information Center and facilitating the formation of Tourism Awareness Groups (Pokdarwis) and providing training related to tourist destination management. Support from the Regional Government includes, among other things, the construction of facilities and infrastructure:

- Prepare a Detailed Spatial Planning Plan for tourist village areas, regulate zoning, and set development standards. Integrate tourist village development into Regional Spatial Planning so that tourist villages are recognized and receive legal protection.
- Building bridges and public transportation facilities to facilitate access to villages; building or repairing facilities such as schools, health centers, places of worship, and markets; improving drainage and irrigation systems to prevent flooding and support agriculture; and ensuring the availability of electricity and clean water in tourist villages.
- Training in homestay management, making craft products, and tourist services. Also support for organizing tourist events to promote tourist villages, such as cultural festivals or sports competitions.
- Formation of tourism awareness groups, as well as training to improve the quality of tourism services and products.
- Simplification of licensing bureaucracy to make things easier for business actors in the tourism sector. Assisting the community in processing tourism business permits.

Government support plays a very important role in improving the quality of tourist villages in Bogor district. Creating an environment that supports sustainable, inclusive tourism development and provides economic benefits for the community.

2. Analysis and Mapping of the Five Hierarchies of Tourist Needs

Identification and mapping of the **hierarchy of tourist needs** revealed the fact that most of the tourist needs that were met were level 1 to level 3:

Level 1 is satisfaction for the five senses, enjoying the natural beauty in tourist villages such as Situbaginda Park, tea plantations, the flow of the Cimandiri river, pine forests, Cilember waterfall, natural beauty, and the charm of terraced rice fields). This need is also complemented by the availability of food and drink facilities. Access to clean water is available at various points, as well as comfortable accommodation in the tourist village of Bogor district.

Level 2 is a touch of emotion in the form of joy, pleasure, and beautiful memories in tourist villages such as enjoying wedang pala or wedang layang, walking in a pine forest, or tea garden. Security is met with the availability of security posts and guard officers who are ready to help.

Outdoor safety guides and health and medical services posts.

Level 3 (impressive interactions with residents and facilities available in tourist villages, especially ecotourism, camping ground, butterfly garden, interactions while learning karawitan batik, cycling, and interactions at camps around the Cihideung Udik dam). Interaction between tourists and the community can be established through tourism education and cultural tourism programs.

Level 4 of the hierarchy of needs is the satisfaction that strengthens tourists' self-development. The need to be recognized or appreciated can be fulfilled through Instagram Mable photo spots, certificates, or awards for participation in an activity or program, for example, planting trees, or souvenirs typical of tourist villages.

Level 5, which allows tourists' self-actualization has not been fully fulfilled. This need is met through educational tourism and nature activities where tourists can develop new skills and knowledge. Volunteer and conservation programs, and cultural and spiritual festivals.

Table 2: Fulfillment of the Hierarchy of Needs Level 1 to Level 5

No	The Brand Component– Need Hierarchy Linkage (Pearce, 1991; Davis, 2002)	Pasir	Taman	Batu	Cilember	Benteng	Cihdeung
		Eurih	Sari	Layang			Udik
1.	Physiological Needs/ Functional: Fulfilling tourists' physical needs to enjoy the five senses, for example, food, drink, natural beauty, etc	Natural Sibaginda Park Jalatunda Well	Natural Tea Garden	Natural Cimandiri River	Natural Pine Forest Cilember Waterfall	Natural Natural beauty	Natural Terraced Rice Field
2.	Intangible: Fulfilling the need for security, comfort, safety, easy access, and friendly service, without worries	Wedang Pala	Tea Garden	Kembar Waterfall Wedang Layang	Wood Flower Pine forest	Hydroponik Cassava Village	Tea Garden Pine Forest
3.	Relationship Needs: The interactions and experiences while in the tourist village impressed the visitors/tourists	Sibaginda Park	Eco-tourism	Eco-tourism Camping Glamping	Butterfly Park Ulin Lembur	Ciwitan batik Catfish Biofloc	Cycling Training Camping near Dam
4.	Self-Esteem/Self-Development Needs: The tourist atmosphere and experience make tourists feel that their status has been elevated because of the unique and valuable experience	Creative Economy Making shoes, sandals	Kasmara n studio Agro tourism	Agro tourism Tracking	Creative Economy Agro tourism Tracking	Batik Agro tourism guava	Camping near Dam Tracking Training
5.	Fulfillment Needs: A travel experience that allows tourists to experience unique experiences, creating unforgettable self-expression and self-actualization	Cultural Arts Performance	Edu tourism Religion tourism	ATV Offroad Outbond	Learn Pencak Silat	Edu tourism Learn batik Cawitan	Craft Cook Tracking

Based on the table above, there are additional notes that need to be made, especially related to the efforts of tourist villages to fulfill tourist needs up to level 4 and level 5.

2. Analysis of Marketing Communication Model Development

There are several important notes for developing a Marketing Communication model based on Fill's model, first, efforts to provide stimulus in the form of strengthening the packaging of serial thematic messages as Two-way dialogic and interactive content (messages) in online media and social media need to be consistent with interpersonal communication messages related to the uniqueness and distinctiveness of tourist destinations. This is important for strengthening the identity of tourist destinations (destination brand identity).

Second, the interaction of tourists with nature and residents of tourist villages has been carried out well following Sundanese hospitality as a culture that is inherent in their daily lives. However, more intensive involvement through learning about creative and creative products, arts and culture, and other facilities can still be improved to strengthen ties with tourists and create unforgettable deep impressions following the five hierarchies of tourist needs.

Third, the management of online media and social media is still done on a part-time basis and has not been carried out more intensively or with planned messages to create a three-layer communication effect as mentioned in Fill's marketing communication model, namely: introduction and understanding (awareness), memorable experiences, and closer involvement (involvement) of tourists in learning cultural arts and food processing or traditional cakes.

In relation to media management, the categorization of the concept of PESO Media (Paid, Earned, Shared, and Owned) is currently developing, namely, media that is used for a fee, media for publicity or reporting, media that contributes to distribution, and media that is owned by a person or organization. including tourist villages.

Fourth, communication patterns with tourists so far have been balanced between introducing the uniqueness of tourist villages or providing deeper understanding (cognitive processing) with efforts to touch feelings or increase liking for the tour packages offered (emotion, feeling, likeability). However, the communication pattern needs to be adapted to the tourist market segment in terms of age, and occupation (tour packages for students, students, community, workers, professions, and so on).

Regarding the various communication patterns with tourists, there are many choices of strategies and programs in the marketing communications mix, such as advertising, sales promotions, publicity or public relations, personal sales, events, sponsorships, direct communication, and interactive marketing communications digital (Fill Chris, 2009), (Duncan T, 2005), (Belch, G. E., & Belch, 2018), (Shimp, T, 2013), (Tuckwell, 2013)

Based on several layers of considerations above, starting from Stimulus, Interaction of tourists in tourist village destinations, management of various media, as well as communication patterns with tourists (starting from introducing, providing understanding, arousing emotions or liking, to encouraging behavior), the Communication Model The marketing of the Tourist Village Destinations that we offer is as shown in the picture on the following page.

This model begins with a tourist village destination that needs to have a tourist village attraction (Tourist Destination Attractiveness) in the form of uniqueness or distinctiveness to be offered (supply-side) to tourists, at least three to five of the ten tourist attractions that have been discussed. On the tourist side (demand-side), they have diverse and hierarchical needs (Tourist Need Hierarchy) as has been explained in the form of five hierarchies of tourist needs. The supply side (the uniqueness of the tourist village) and the demand side (tourist needs) need to be in harmony and there is an intersection so that tourists are interested and want to visit. For this reason, the role of designing a Tourist Destination Brand (Tourist Destination Branding) is very strategic in bringing together the unique side of a tourist village with the hierarchy of tourist needs.

Figure 7: Village Tourism Destination Marketing Communiacion Model

The next stage is to design a marketing communication mix strategy and program (marketing mix) following the tourist segment and the specified tourism village communication objectives. For this reason, it is necessary to choose the combination of media used, such as the PESO media categorization (Paid, Earned, Shared, and Owned), mentioned above. The terms currently used are no longer top-line media, bottom-line media, and outdoor media. The aim is to build closer relationships with stakeholders (Stakeholder Engagement), not just closeness with tourists.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Based on mapping the attractiveness of tourist villages, five unique elements were found for developing destination brands (destination branding): natural beauty (ecotourism) and agrotourism, tourism based on learning with nature (edutourism), arts and culture attractions and learning (cultural tourism), adventure in nature (adventure), and creative economy

learning. The results of mapping the hierarchy of tourist needs that were fulfilled were only level 1 (satisfaction of the five senses enjoying the tourist village), level 2 (emotional touch in the form of joy and beautiful memories in the tourist village), and level 3 (interaction with residents and tourist village facilities). Level 4 of the hierarchy of needs is satisfaction for tourists' self-development and level 5, namely tourists' self-actualization, has not been fully fulfilled.

Recommendations for strengthening the attractiveness of tourist villages are mainly related to highlighting the uniqueness or distinctiveness of tourist villages so that they become a differentiating identity that is sought after by tourists (destination brand identity). Recommendations related to the hierarchy of tourist needs to increase interest in visiting are making efforts in tourist villages to fulfill tourist needs up to level 4 so that tourists feel they get benefits or added value and level 5 so that tourists feel they gain a sense of pride and self-actualization by visiting tourist villages.

Recommendations for developing a Marketing Communication model based on Fill's model are as follows:

- 1) Packaging serial thematic messages as content (messages) in online media and social media that are consistent with interpersonal communication messages.
- 2) Strengthen the uniqueness, distinctiveness, or identity of tourist destinations (destination brand identity).
- 3) Tourist interaction with nature and more intensive involvement through learning about creative and creative products, arts and culture, and other facilities.
- 4) More intensive management of online media and social media; and
- 5) Sharpen the tourist market segment according to the tour packages offered.

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